

<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2024.01.06>

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:18FD2F2D-8D80-40F6-A54B-D4B7B36CA61F>

● Taxonomy notes on twenty-four spider species (Arachnida: Araneae) from China

Ye-Jie LIN

Imperial College London, London SW7 2AZ, United Kingdom; [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6789-2731) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6789-2731>; linyejie15@gmail.com

Abstract: Twenty-four spider species from China were studied, including fifteen new national records, two new combinations, four new synonyms, and three species are considered as *nomina dubia* due to the loss of the holotype and unclear descriptions.

Keywords: New combination, new record, new synonym, *nomen dubium*

● 中国二十四种蜘蛛的分类学评述（蛛形纲：蜘蛛目）

林业杰

帝国理工学院，伦敦 SW7 2AZ，英国

摘要：本文对来自中国的 24 种蜘蛛进行了研究，其中包括 15 个中国新记录种，2 个新组合，4 个新异名，并且由于正模标本的丢失和描述不清晰，将 3 种蜘蛛视为疑名。

关键词：新组合，新记录，新异名，疑名

Citation: Lin Y-J 2024: Taxonomy notes on twenty-five spider species (Arachnida: Araneae) from China. *The Indochina Entomologist*, 1 (6): 35–48. [林业杰 2024: 中国二十五种蜘蛛的分类学评述（蛛形纲：蜘蛛目）。中南半岛昆虫学家, 1 (6): 35–48.]

<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2024.01.06>

Accepted by Cheng-Bin WANG: 27.X.2024; published online: 28.X.2024

Copyright Ye-Jie Lin. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CCBY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Introduction

Nearly 100 new species of spiders are discovered every year in China. Chinese Arachnologists are also increasing by years. However, little research has been done on reviewing spider species published before the 21st century, and species published in that period were always described in Chinese and simply illustrated, posing a risk to spider research in China and around the world.

Due to the lack of proper management and frequent changes in specimen storage institutions in China, examining type specimens has become a challenge. On account of the inability to find type specimens, taxonomic research on many Chinese species has stagnated. Therefore, solving this issue has become a significant challenge in China. This paper takes a relatively bold approach to provide a scientifically grounded solution to this problem.

In this paper, through the study of 24 species from China, 15 species are newly record from China, 4 new synonyms are proposed, and 3 species are considered as *nomina dubia*.

Material and methods

All specimens were preserved in 80% ethanol. The spermathecae were cleared in trypsin enzyme solution to dissolve non-chitinous tissues. Specimens were examined, illustrated, photographed and measured using a Leica M205C stereomicroscope equipped with a Leica DFC420 Camera and LAS software (Ver. 4.0). Photographs were stacked with Helicon Focus® (v. 7.6.1) and processed in Adobe Photoshop CC2022®.

For each species only the following synonyms and references are given in the text: original description, taxonomic status change. For other references, see World Spider Catalog (2024).

The material examined for this study is deposited in the following collections: **CYJL**—collection of Ye-Jie Lin, Dalian, China; **HKUDE**—Department of Ecology, University of Hong Kong, Hongkong, China; **HNU**—College of Life Sciences, Hunan Normal University, Changsha, China; **HSU**—Huangshan University (formerly called Huizhou Junior Teacher's College), Huangshan, China; **IRRI**—International Rice Research Institute, Entomology Division, Manila, Philippines; **JLU**—Jilin University (formerly called Nonnan Bethune University of Medical Sciences), Changchun, China; **MHBU**—Museum of Hebei University, Baoding, China; **SDU**—Shandong University (SDU), Jinan, China.

Taxonomy

Family Araneidae Clerck, 1757

Genus *Argiope* Audouin, 1826

Type species. *Aranea sericea* Olivier, 1789.

Argiope chloreis Thorell, 1877

Fig. 1

Argiope chloreis Thorell, 1877: 368 (♀).

Argiope pumila Thorell, 1890: 99 (♀).

Material examined. 1 ♀ China, Yunnan, Pu'er City, Jiangcheng County, 24–19.VII.2022, Fan Gao leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Yunnan) **new national record**; Malaysia (peninsula, Borneo), Indonesia (Sumatra, Sulawesi).

Genus *Paraplectana* Brito Capello, 1867

Type species. *Eurysoma thorntoni* Blackwall, 1865.

Paraplectana mamoniae Basumatary & Brahma, 2019

Fig. 2

FIGURE 1. *Argiope chloreis* Thorell, 1877, female, in life. Photoed by Fan Gao.

FIGURE 2. *Paraplectana mamoniae* Basumatary & Brahma, 2019, female, in life. Photoed by Fan Gao.

Paraplectana mamoniae Basumatary & Brahma, 2019: 276, figs 1–16 (♀).

Material examined. 1♀ China, Yunnan, Pu'er City, Jiangcheng County, 24–19.VII.2022, Fan Gao leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Yunnan) **new national record**; India.

Genus *Poltys* C. L. Koch, 1843

Type species. *Poltys illepidus* C. L. Koch, 1843.

Poltys stygius Thorell, 1898

Poltys stygius Thorell, 1898: 344 (♀).

Poltys microtuberculatus Rainbow, 1916: 118, pl. 22, fig. 44 (♀).

Material examined. 1♀ China, Guangdong, Shenzhen City, Nanshan District, Tanglang Mountain, 24–19.VII.2022, Qian-Le Lu leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Guangdong) **new national record**; Myanmar to Australia (Queensland).

Family Cicurinidae F. O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1893

Genus *Cicurina* Menge, 1871

Type species. *Aranea cicurea* Fabricius, 1793.

Cicurina calyciforma Wang & Xu, 1989

Cicurina calyciforma Wang & Xu, 1989: 4, figs 1–7 (♂♀).

Cybaeus desmaeus Zhu & Wang, 1992: 343, figs 6–7 (♀). **Syn. nov.**

Type materials. *Cicurina calyciforma*: Holotype ♀, China, Anhui, Huangshan City, Qiyun Mountain, 26.X.1983, Ya-Jun Xu and Lin Wang leg., not examined (HNU); Allotype ♂, same data as holotype, not examined (HNU); Paratypes 4♂5♀, same data as holotype, not examined (HSU).

Cybaeus desmaeus: Holotype ♀, China, Anhui, Huangshan, 27.X.1974, Chuan-Dian Zhu leg., not examined (JLU).

Diagnosis. See Wang and Xu, 1989.

Distribution. China (Anhui).

Comments. No differences between *Ci. calyciforma* and *Cy. desmaeus* were observed. Thus, I consider *Cy. desmaeus* to be the junior synonym of *Ci. calyciforma*.

Family Cybaeidae Banks, 1892

Genus *Cybaeus* L. Koch, 1868

Type species. *Amaurobius tetricus* C. L. Koch, 1839.

Cybaeus bam Marusik & Logunov, 1991

Cybaeus bam Marusik & Logunov, 1991: 88, figs 1.5, 3.3 (♀).

Material examined. 3♀ China, Liaoning, Fushun City, Qingyuan Manchu Autonomous County, Dahu Forest Farm, Chinese Academy of Sciences Forest Ecology Observation Station, 42.5878°N, 124.9367°E, elev. 352 m, 08.IX.2019, Peng-Yu Jin and Ye-Jie Lin leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Liaoning) **new national record**; Russia (Kurile Island).

Family Dictynidae O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1871

Genus *Paratheuma* Bryant, 1940

Type species. *Eutichurus insulanus* Banks, 1902.

***Paratheuma insulana* (Banks, 1902)**

Eutichurus insulanus Banks, 1902: 270, fig. 3 (♀).

Paratheuma insulana Bryant, 1940: 387, pl. 11, fig. 148 (♀).

Material examined. 1♂1♀ China, Hainan, Haikou City, Wanlü Garden, 10.IV.2020, Qian-Le Lu leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Hainan) **new national record**; USA, Caribbean, Japan.

***Paratheuma shirahamaensis* (Oi, 1960)**

Litisedes shirahamaensis Oi, 1960: 7, figs 10–15 (♂♀).

Litisedes shirahamensis Irie, 1985: 7, figs. 18–19 (♂♀).

Paratheuma shirahamaense Yaginuma, 1990: 2, figs. 1–4 (♂♀).

Material examined. 1♂1♀ China, Shandong, Qingdao City, Shinan District, Second Seaside Bathing Beach, near Donghai Grand Hotel, 36.0484°N, 120.3411°E, 16.VII.2023, Zi-Xu Yin leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Shandong) **new national record**; Korea, Japan.

Family Eresidae C. L. Koch, 1845**Genus *Stegodyphus* Simon, 1873**

Type species. *Eresus lineatus* Latreille, 1817.

***Stegodyphus lineatus* (Latreille, 1817)**

Eresus lineatus Latreille, 1817: vol. 10, p. 393 (♀).

Eresus acanthophilus Dufour, 1820: 302, pl. 95, figs 3–4 (♂♀).

Eresus unifasciatus C. L. Koch, 1846: 5, fig. 1081 (♀).

Eresus adpersus C. L. Koch, 1846: 8, fig. 1083 (♀).

Eresus fuscifrons C. L. Koch, 1846: 9, fig. 1084 (♀).

Stegodyphus molitor Simon, 1873: 338.

Eresus arenarius Kroneberg, 1875: 44, pl. 5, fig. 32 (♂).

Stegodyphus lineatus Pavesi, 1876: 443.

Stegodyphus lineatus deserticola Simon, 1908: 79.

Stegodyphus quadriculatus Franganillo, 1926: 75.

Material examined. 1♂3♀ China, Xinjiang, Ili Kazakh Autonomous Prefecture, Huocheng County, Tukai Desert, 20.VI.2017, Lei Zhang leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Xinjiang) **new national record**; Southern Europe, North Africa to Tajikistan.

Family Gnaphosidae Banks, 1892**Genus *Hongkongia* Song & Zhu, 1998**

Type species. *Hongkongia wuae* Song & Zhu, 1998 (= *Geodrassus ellenae* Barrion & Litsinger, 1995).

***Hongkongia ellenae* (Barrion & Litsinger, 1995) comb. nov.**

Geodrassus ellenae Barrion & Litsinger, 1995: 194, figs 112a–d, 113a–g (♂♀).

Hongkongia wuae Song & Zhu, 1998: 104, fig. 1A–E (♂). **Syn. nov.**

Type material. *Geodrassus ellenae*: Holotype ♀: Philippines, Luzon Island, Quezon, Real, Llavac Village, 18.I.1985, A.T. Barrion and M. Perez leg., not examined (IRRI); Paratype ♂ and one immature male, 14.V.1985, M. Perez and R. Apostol. leg., not examined (IRRI).

Hongkongia wuae: Holotype ♂: China, Hongkong, New Territories, Duong Dong, elev. 40 m, 19.III.2009, K.-Y. Wu, not

examined (HKUDE).

Diagnosis. See Lin & Li (2023).

Distribution. China (Hongkong, Yunnan), Philippines.

Comments. The male embolus bulb shows that *Geodrassus ellenae* belongs to the genus *Hongkongia*, so I hereby transfer this species to *Hongkongia*. No differences between the holotype of *H. ellenae* **comb. nov.** and female of *H. wuae* in Lin & Li (2023) were observed. Thus, I consider *H. wuae* to be a junior synonym of *H. ellenae* **comb. nov.**

Family Hersiliidae Thorell, 1869

Genus *Hersilia* Audouin, 1826

Type species. *Hersilia caudata* Audouin, 1826.

Hersilia vicina Baehr & Baehr, 1993

Fig. 3A, B

Hersilia vicina Baehr & Baehr, 1993: 22, fig. 18e–f (♀).

Hersilia vicina Chami-Kranon, Wongsawad & Dankittipakul, 2007: 687, figs 1–9 (♂♀).

Material examined. 1♂1♀ China, Yunnan, Pu'er City, Jiangcheng County, 24–19.VII.2022, Fan Gao leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Yunnan) **new national record**; Thailand.

Family Liocranidae Simon, 1897

Genus *Rhaeboctesis* Simon, 1897

Type species. *Rhaeboctesis equestris* Simon, 1897.

Rhaeboctesis xizangensis (Hu, 2001) **comb. nov.**

Fig. 4A–G

Sagella xizangensis Hu, 2001: 316, figs 187.1–4 (♂♀).

Sagellula xizangensis Jäger & Yin, 2001: 131.

Type materials. Holotype ♀, China, Tibet, Xigaze, elev. ca 3800 m, 2.II.1982, Sheng-Chang Hu leg., not examined (SDU); Allotype. ♂ same data as holotype, not examined (SDU); Paratypes, 1♂2♀, Tibet, Namling, elev. ca 4100 m, 6.IV.1984, Qiong-Qiong Pu leg.; 1♂2♀, Tibet, Nyingchi, elev. ca 3000 m, 9.IX.1989, Bei-Ping Zhang leg., not examined (SDU).

Other materials. 2♂1♀, China, Tibet, Nyingchi City, Bomi County, Baka Village, 29.8752°N, 95.5522°E, 18.X.2021, Qian-Le Lu leg. (CYJL).

Diagnosis. This species can be distinguished from other congeners by the small, hook-shaped TA and in female the hood as long as atrium (Fig. 1).

Description. See Hu (2001).

Distribution. China (Tibet).

Comments. This species has a similar general genitalic morphology to *Rhaeboctesis*, with the broad anterior hood and lateral hoods in the epigyne and the broadly curved distal embolus and hook-shaped median apophysis on the palp.

Family Nesticidae Simon, 1894

Genus *Nesticella* Lehtinen & Saaristo, 1980

Type species. *Nesticus nepalensis* Hubert, 1973.

FIGURE 3. *Hersilia vicina* Baehr & Baehr, 1993, in life. Photoed by Fan Gao: **A** male **B** female.

FIGURE 4. *Rhaeboctesis xizangensis* (Hu, 2001) **comb. nov.:** **A** male habitus, dorsal view **B** female habitus, dorsal view **C** epigyne, ventral view **D** vulva, dorsal view **E** left male palp, prolateral view **F** same, ventral view **G** same, retrolateral view. **Abbreviations:** C—conductor, CD—copulatory duct, CO—copulatory opening, E—embolus, EP—epigynal pocket, FD—fertilization duct, H—hood, RTA—retrolateral tibial apophysis, SD—sperm duct, S—spermatheca, ST—subtegulum, TA—tegular apophysis, T—tegulum.

***Nesticella beccus* Grall & Jäger, 2016**

Nesticella beccus Grall & Jäger, 2016: 251, figs 10–13, 26–27, 33–34 (♂♀).

Material examined. 1♂3♀ China, Yunnan, Xishuangbanna Autonomous Prefecture, Dadugang, 26.VI.2022, Ma-Ze Hao and Ye-Jie Lin leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Yunnan) **new national record**; Laos, Thailand.

Family Salticidae Blackwall, 1841

Genus *Epeus* G. W. Peckham & E. G. Peckham, 1886

Type species. *Evenus tener* Simon, 1877.

***Epeus tener* (Simon, 1877)**

Fig. 5

Evenus tener Simon, 1877: 59, pl. 3, fig. 12 (♀).

Epeus tener Peckham & Peckham, 1886: 334.

Viciria cristata Thorell, 1887: 393 (♂).

Viciria tenera Simon, 1903: 743, 752, figs 882–883 (♂).

Material examined. 1♂1♀ China, Yunnan, Pu'er City, Simao District, 25.VII.2022, Fan Gao leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Yunnan) **new national record**; Myanmar, Thailand, Vietnam, Indonesia (Java, Sulawesi), Philippines (Basilan Island).

FIGURE 5. *Epeus tener* (Simon, 1877), female, in life. Photoed by Fan Gao.

Family Sicariidae Keyserling, 1880

Genus *Loxosceles* Heineken & Lowe, 1832

Type species. *Scytodes rufescens* Dufour, 1820.

Loxosceles aphrasta Wang, 1994 *nomen dubium*

Loxosceles aphrasta Wang, 1994: 13, figs 1–2 (♂♀).

Type materials. *Loxosceles aphrasta*. Holotype ♀, China, Hunan, Ling County, VIII.1982, Jia-Fu Wang leg., not examined (HNU); Allotype ♂, same data as holotype, not examined (HNU); Paratypes 3♀5♂, same data as holotype, not examined (HNU).

Notes. The lost type specimen, lack of clear figures of the type specimens, and the vague distributional information make further study of the taxonomy of this species impossible. I treat it as *nomen dubium*.

Loxosceles lacta Wang, 1994 *nomen dubium*

Loxosceles lacta Wang, 1994: 14, figs 3–4 (♂♀).

Type materials. *Loxosceles aphrasta*. Holotype ♀, China, Hunan, Changsha City, 8.IX.1988, Jia-Fu Wang leg., not examined (HNU); Allotype ♂, same data as holotype, not examined (HNU).

Notes. The lost type specimen, lack of clear figures of the type specimens, and the vague distributional information make further study of the taxonomy of this species impossible. I treat it as *nomen dubium*.

Family Sparassidae Bertkau, 1872

Genus *Heteropoda* Latreille, 1804

Type species. *Aranea venatoria* Linnaeus, 1767 from North America.

Heteropoda jiangxiensis Li, 1991 *nomen dubium*

Heteropoda jiangxiensis Li, 1991: 367, figs 5–6 (♀).

Type material. *Heteropoda jiangxiensis*. Holotype ♀, China, Jiangxi, Yifeng County, 8.VII.1989, Ai-Hua Li and Sheng-Chang Hu leg., lost. (A plant protective station in Ganzhou, Xiao-Di Shi from Ganzhou, personal communication).

Notes. The lost type specimen, lack of clear figures of the type specimens, and the vague distributional information make further study of the taxonomy of this species impossible. I treat it as *nomen dubium*.

Genus *Sinopoda* Jäger, 1999

Type species. *Sarotes forcipatus* Karsch, 1881.

Sinopoda tralinh Grall & Jäger, 2020

Sinopoda tralinh Grall & Jäger, 2020: 72, figs 47a–b, 65a–b (♀).

Material examined. 1♀ China, Guangxi, Baise City, Napo County, Hexiang, 23.VI.2023, Jia-Jun Zhou leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Guangxi) **new national record**; Vietnam.

Genus *Thymoites* Keyserling, 1884

Type species. *Thymoites crassipes* Keyserling, 1884.

Thymoites ulleungensis (Paik, 1991)

Savignia ulleungensis Paik, 1991: 7, figs 1–13 (♂).

Thymoites ulleungensis Eskov, 1992: 167.

Material examined. 2♂ China, Beijing, Mentougou District, Jingxilinchang, 26.X.2022, Jin-Cheng Liu leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Beijing) **new national record**; Korea.

Family Thomisidae Sundevall, 1833**Genus *Alcimochthes* Simon, 1885**

Type species. *Alcimochthes limbatus* Simon, 1885.

***Alcimochthes limbatus* Simon, 1885**

Alcimochthes limbatus Simon, 1885: 448, pl. 10, fig. 16 (♂♀).

Lysiteles hongkong Song, Zhu & Wu, 1997: 82, fig. 3A–B (♀). **Syn. nov.**

Lysiteles guangxiensis He & Hu, 1999: 8, figs 1–3 (♂).

Tmarus shuquianglii Barrion, Barrion-Dupo & Heong, 2013: 42, fig. 48A–E (♂).

Type material. *Lysiteles hongkong*: Holotype ♀ China, Hongkong, New Territories, Lujing, 11.VIII.1995, not examined (HKUDE).

Description and diagnosis. See Ono (1988) for a redescription and diagnosis of both sexes.

Distribution. China (Hainan, Hunan, Sichuan, Taiwan, Zhejiang); Malaysia, Singapore, Vietnam, Japan.

Comments. No differences between *Alcimochthes limbatus* and *Lysiteles hongkong* could be distinguished. Thus, I consider *L. hongkong* to be a junior synonym of *A. limbatus*.

Genus *Ozyptila* Simon, 1864

Type species. *Thomisus claveatus* Walckenaer, 1837.

***Ozyptila lugubris* (Kroneberg, 1875)**

Xysticus lugubris Kroneberg, 1875: 35, pl. 3, fig. 23 (♂♀).

Ozyptila lugubris Simon, 1889: 381.

Material examined. 1 ♀ China, Xinjiang, Ili Kazakh Autonomous Prefecture, Beside the Duna Expressway, 43.5861°N, 82.6352°E, 7.IV.2023, Wen-Tao Huo leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Xinjiang) **new national record**; Kazakhstan, Iran, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan.

Genus *Xysticus* C. L. Koch, 1835

Type species. *Aranea audax* Schrank, 1803.

***Xysticus idolothytus* Logunov, 1995**

Xysticus albomaculatus Utochkin, 1968: 18, figs. 102–103 (♂).

Xysticus idolothytus Logunov, 1995: 112, fig. 1A–B (♂).

Material examined. 2 ♂ China, Gansu, Zhangye City, Gaotai County, Xitan Village, 39.3505°N, 99.5717°E, elev. 1408m, 7.IV.2023, Qian-Le Lu leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Gansu) **new national record**; Kazakhstan, Mongolia.

Family Zodariidae Thorell, 1881**Genus *Zodariellum* Andreeva & Tystshenko, 1968**

Type species. *Zodariellum surprisum* Andreeva & Tystshenko, 1968.

***Zodariellum nenilini* (Eskov, 1995)**

Zodarion nenilini Eskov, in Eskov & Marusik, 1995: 62, figs 27–29 (♂♀).

Acanthozodium nenilini Marusik & Logunov, 1999: 253.

Zodariellum nenilini Marusik & Koponen, 2001: 42, figs 1, 6, 10–13, 19–24 (♂♀).

Material examined. 1 ♂ 1 ♀ China, Xinjiang, Ili Kazakh Autonomous Prefecture, Yining City, Tiechanggou, 6.V.2022, Sheng Du leg. (CYJL).

Distribution. China (Xinjiang) **new national record**; Kazakhstan, Mongolia.

Family Zoropsidae Bertkau, 1882

Genus *Takeoa* Lehtinen, 1967

Type species. *Zoropsis nishimurai* Yaginuma, 1963.

Takeoa nishimurai (Yaginuma, 1963)

Zoropsis nishimurai Yaginuma, 1963: 1, 3, pl. I, pl. III, figs 1–12 (♂♀).

Takeoa nishimurai Lehtinen, 1967: 266, figs 403, 405 (♂♀).

Zoropsis coreana Kim & Cho, 2002: 187, figs 379–384 (♀).

Takeoa huangshan Tang, Xu & Zhu, 2004: 706, figs 1–5 (♂). **Syn. nov.**

Type material. Holotype of *T. nishimurai* ♂, China: Anhui, Minzhu Town, Huang Mountain, 118°06'N, 33°E, 9.VIII.2002, Xin-Sheng Tang and Zhi-Shung Song leg., not examined (MHBU).

Diagnosis. See Yaginuma (1963).

Distribution. China (Zhejiang, Anhui, Hunan); Korea, Japan.

Comments. Holotype of *Takeoa nishimurai* was examined by Bosselaers (2002), and in Tang *et al.* 2004, diagnostic differences of *T. huangshan* are eight ventral spine pairs instead of seven on tibia I. However, this is a very variable character in many specimens and the bifurcated embolus is also present in *T. nishimurai* (Bosselaers, personal communication). Thus, I consider *T. huangshan* to be the junior synonym of *T. nishimurai*.

Discussion

A summary of the taxonomic status changes of the spider species mentioned in this paper is listed as follow:

1. *Alcimochthes limbatus* = *Lysiteles hongkong* **syn. nov.**
2. *Cicurina calyciforma* = *Cybaeus desmaeus* **syn. nov.**
3. *Hongkongia ellenae* **comb. nov.** = *Geodrassus ellenae* = *Hongkongia wuae* **syn. nov.**
5. *Loxosceles aphrasta* **nomen dubium**
6. *Loxosceles lacta* **nomen dubium**
7. *Heteropoda jiangxiensis* **nomen dubium**
8. *Rhaeboctesis xizangensis* **comb. nov.** = *Sagellula xizangensis*
9. *Takeoa nishimurai* = *Takeoa huangshan* **syn. nov.**

Acknowledgements

The manuscript benefited greatly from comments by Charles R. Haddad (University of the Free State, South Africa), Jan Bosselaers (Royal Museum for Central Africa, Tervuren of Belgium), Cheng-Bin Wang and Hao Xu (both Mianyang Normal University, Sichuan, China). Thanks are given to my friends Fan Gao (Jiangsu, China), Han Dong (Hubei, China), Jia-Jun Zhou (Zhejiang, China), Jiang-Wei Zheng (Hubei, China), Peng-Yu Jin (Beijing, China), Qian-Le Lu (Guangdong, China), Sheng Du (Xinjiang, China), Wen-Tao Huo (Beijing, China), Yang Zhong (Hubei, China), Ze-Hao Ma (Yunnan, China) and Zi-Xu Yin (Shandong, China) for their field work.

References

- Baehr M & Baehr B 1993: The Hersiliidae of the Oriental Region including New Guinea. Taxonomy, phylogeny, zoogeography (Arachnida, Araneae). *Spixiana*, 19 (Suppl.): 1–95.
- Barrión AT & Litsinger JA 1995: *Riceland spiders of South and Southeast Asia*. CAB International, Wallingford, UK, 700 pp., 16 pls.

- Basumatary P & Brahma D 2019: A new species of *Paraplectana* Brito Capello, 1867 (Araneae: Araneidae) from north-east India. *Arachnology*, 18 (3): 276–279.
<https://doi.org/10.13156/ arac.2019.18.3.276>
- Bosselaers J 2002: A cladistic analysis of Zoropsidae (Araneae), with the description of a new genus. *Belgian Journal of Zoology*, 132: 141–154.
- Chami-Kranon T, Wongsawad C & Dankittipakul P 2007: Description of the male of *Hersilia vicina* Baehr & Baehr, 1993 from northeastern Thailand, with notes on the *albomaculata*-group (Araneae, Hersiliidae). *Revue Suisse de Zoologie*, 114: 685–692.
- Grall E & Jäger P 2016: Four new species of the spider genus *Nesticella* Lehtinen & Saaristo, 1980 from Laos, Thailand and Myanmar and the first description of the male of *Nesticella yui* Wunderlich & Song, 1995 with a proposed new diagnostic character for the family Nesticidae Simon, 1894 (Arachnida, Araneae). *Zootaxa*, 4085 (2): 248–264.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4085.2.5>
- Grall E & Jäger P 2020: Forty-seven new species of *Sinopoda* from Asia with a considerable extension of the distribution range to the south and description of a new species group (Sparassidae: Heteropodinae). *Zootaxa*, 4797 (1): 1–101.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4797.1.1>
- Hu J-L 2001: *Spiders in Qinghai-Tibet Plateau of China*. Henan Science and Technology Publishing House, Zhengzhou, 658 pp. [胡金林 2001: 青藏高原蜘蛛. 河南科学技术出版社, 郑州, 658 pp.]
- Kastrygina ZA & Kovblyuk MM 2013: A review of the spider genus *Thanatus* C.L. Koch, 1837 in Crimea (Aranei: Philodromidae). *Arthropoda Selecta*, 22 (3): 239–254.
<https://doi.org/10.15298/arthsel.22.3.07>
- Li A-H 1991: Two new species of spiders of the genus *Heteropoda* from China (Araneae: Heteropodidae). *Acta Agriculturae Universitatis Jiangxiensis*, 13 (4): 366–370. [李爱华 1991: 我国南方巨蟹蛛属两新种 (蜘蛛目: 巨蟹蛛科). 江西农业大学学报, 13 (4): 366–370.]
- Lin Y-J & Li S-Q 2023: On nine ground spiders from Xishuangbanna, China (Araneae, Gnaphosidae), including two new genera and seven new species. *ZooKeys*, 1174: 141–174.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1174.106340>
- Logunov DV 1995: Contribution to the northern Asian fauna of the crab spider genus *Xysticus* C. L. Koch, 1835 (Aranei Thomisidae). *Arthropoda Selecta*, 3 (3–4): 111–118.
- Marusik YM & Logunov DV 1991: Spiders of the superfamily Amaurobioidea (Aranei) from Sakhalin and Kurily Islands. *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal*, 70 (9): 87–94.
- Marusik YM & Mikhailov KG 2021: Revalidation of *Xysticus tuberosus* Thorell, 1875 (Aranei: Thomisidae) with notes on the related species. *Arthropoda Selecta*, 30 (1): 119–124.
<https://doi.org/10.15298/arthsel.30.1.11>
- Miller JA, Griswold CE, Scharff N, Řezáč M, Szűts T & Marhabaie M 2012: The velvet spiders: an atlas of the Eresidae (Arachnida, Araneae). *ZooKeys*, 195: 1–144.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.195.2342>
- Ono H 1988: *A revisional study of the spider family Thomisidae (Arachnida, Araneae) of Japan*. National Science Museum, Tokyo, 252 pp.
- Ono H 2006: Spiders from the coastal areas of the Sagami Sea, Japan (Arachnida, Araneae). *Memoirs of the National Science Museum Tokyo*, 42: 255–274.
- Paik K-Y 1991: Four new species of the linyphiid spiders from Korea (Araneae: Linyphiidae). *Korean Arachnology*, 7: 1–17.
- Prószyński J & Deeleman-Reinhold CL 2012: Description of some Salticidae (Aranei) from the Malay archipelago. II. Salticidae of Java and Sumatra, with comments on related species. *Arthropoda Selecta*, 21 (1): 29–60.
<https://doi.org/10.15298/arthsel.21.1.04>
- Smith HM 2006: A revision of the genus *Polrys* in Australasia (Araneae: Araneidae). *Records of the Australian Museum*, 58: 43–96.
- Song D-X, Zhu M-S & Wu K-Y 1997: Some new species of the spiders from Hong Kong. *Acta Arachnologica Sinica*, 6 (2): 81–86. [宋大祥, 朱明生 & 胡嘉仪 1997: 香港蜘蛛数新种记述. 蛛形学报, 6 (2): 81–86.]
- Tan J, Chan Z-Y, Wong C-X, Koh JHK & Yong H-S 2019: Morphological and molecular evidence supports *Argiope chloreis* Thorell

- 1877 and *A. chloreides* Chrysanthus 1961 (Araneidae: Argiopinae) as distinct species. *Acta Arachnologica*, 68 (2): 41–58.
<https://doi.org/10.2476/asjaa.68.41>
- Tang X-S, Xu Y-J & Zhu M-S 2004: A new species of the genus *Takeoa* from China (Araneae, Zoropsidae). *Acta Zootaxonomica Sinica*, 29 (4): 706–707. [唐鑫生, 徐亚君 & 朱明生 2004: 中国塔逸蛛属一新种记述 (蜘蛛目, 逸蛛科). *动物分类学报*, 29 (4): 706–707.]
- Tucker RWE 1920: Contributions to the South African Arachnid Fauna. II. On some new South African spiders of the families Barychelidae, Dipluridae, Eresidae, Zodariidae, Heracliidae, Urocteidae, Clubionidae. *Annals of the South African Museum* 17: 439–488, pls. 28–29.
- Wang J-F 1994: Two new species of spiders of the genus *Loxosceles* from China. *Journal of Hebei Normal University (Natural Science Edition)*, 1994 (Suppl.): 13–15. [王家福 1994: 中国隐蛛属 (刺客蛛科) 两新种记述. *河北师范大学学报 (自然科学版)*, 1994 (Suppl.): 13–15.]
- Wang L-Y, Zhou G-C & Peng X-J 2019: Four new species of the spider genus *Cicurina* Menge, 1871 from China (Araneae: Dictynidae). *Zootaxa*, 4615 (2): 351–364.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4615.2.7>
- World Spider Catalog 2024: *World Spider Catalog. Version 25.5*. Natural History Museum Bern. Available from: <https://wsc.nmbe.ch/> (accessed 27.X.2024).
<https://doi.org/10.24436/2>
- Yoshida H 2003: *The spider family Theridiidae (Arachnida: Araneae) from Japan*. Arachnological Society of Japan, 224 pp.
- Zamani A & Marusik YM 2022: New taxonomic considerations in *Zodariellum* Andreeva & Tyshchenko, 1968 (Araneae: Zodariidae), with notes on the presence of cymbial diverticulum in different zodariid genera. *Zootaxa*, 5178 (2): 161–177.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5178.2.3>
- Zhu C-D & Wang J-F 1992: Four new species of the genus *Cybaeus* from China (Araneae: Agelenidae). *Journal of Norman Bethune University of Medical Sciences*, 18 (4): 342–345. [朱传典 & 王家福 1992: 中国霞蛛属四新种记述 (蜘蛛目: 漏斗蛛科). *白求恩医科大学学报*, 18 (4): 342–345.]

Additional information

Author contributions: The author solely contributed to this work.

Conflict of interest: The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

Data availability: All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

Ethical statement: No ethical statement was reported.

Funding: This study was self-funded by the author.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of *ICE* and/or the editor(s). *ICE* and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.